

The finance-to-macro channel and the cyclicity of the term spread and the term premium

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Introduction

This paper highlights two stylized facts of the US yield curve. First, the term spread and the term premium tend to increase during recessions. Second, there is a high positive correlation between unemployment and both the spread and the term premium. We present a macro-finance model with financial market segmentation and labor market frictions which is consistent with these two facts. We show that only credit supply shocks can explain the positive correlation of the spread and the term premium with unemployment. In contrast, technology shocks are unable to generate the right cyclicity of the term structure.

Methods

Using data from 1971Q4 to 2019Q4, we unveil two empirical regularities: first, the spread and the term premium have increased during all the recessions since the 1980s. Second, there is a high positive correlation between unemployment and these two variables.

We develop a DSGE model with two main ingredients: financial market segmentation (Gertler and Karadi, 2011; Sims and Wu, 2021) and labor market frictions. The short-term bond market is segmented from the long-term bond market because households face portfolio costs for holding long-term bonds. An agency problem between banks and depositors introduces endogenous constraints on leverage ratios, which tie the cost of credit with the banks' balance sheet.

Results

We emphasize three results of our analysis. First, we show that under segmented markets the term premium is primarily a reflection of the degree of limits to arbitrage and the overall soundness of the balance sheet of the financial institutions.

Second, we show that credit supply shocks reduce the amount of funds available for banks to buy long-term bonds, increasing both the spread and the term premium, and producing a persistent recession – in line with the stylized facts.

In contrast, negative technology shocks, often proposed as the driver of positive term premiums during recessions, imply counterfactual term structure dynamics.

References

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